

Appendix A: Matrix

The matrices created by the different methods deliver different values between them, this is given their way of calculating the similarity between images, however after our tests correlation stands out as the best methodology, so it is necessary to understand and visualise the differences that exist between the different similarity matrices created and to identify some pattern that explains the differences between them, that is why this appendix includes the plots that show a correlation matrix versus the other methods, such as CNN and SSIM.

A.1. Figures

Fig. A.1. CNN and SSIM on the Y-axis, and the correlation on the X-axis, both with full frame and with optimization zone respectively, where it can be seen that both the neural network (CNN) and the similarity index (SSIM) do not have the same distribution in terms of which images are the closest, for CNN full frame the values are all very similar, which means that it sees all the images almost the same, and for SSIM although there is a greater diversity of values it also has a difference that for high correlations it has very different values of similarity. ranging from 0 to 0.8.

Appendix B: Environment Variables

One of the challenges of our study was to determine if there were any environmental variables that could explain the quality of a science image. This would allow us to select them without having to use additional calculations, since this information is included in the metadata of our science cubes. The following appendix includes further plots illustrating the different methods used to determine which variable is the most influential in terms of contrast performance at 245 mas, how it performs in image selection, and how it affects the S/N of our science object.

B.1. Figures

Fig. B.1. Histogram of the environmental variables that have the greatest influence on the contrast, as described in section 3.1.4. The most important is the Strehl SPARTA, which we thus used as a comparison metric, with a mean value of 0.78. Then, the r_0 SPARTA with a mean value of 0.23, seeing SPARTA with 0.62 arcsec, IA (Image Analyzer) FWHM with 1.02 arcsec, and finally MASS-DIMM tau0 with 3.7 milliseconds.

Fig. B.2. Bar plot showing the mean Strehl SPARTA vs. contrast percentiles Q , where Q_0 corresponds to the percentile of the best contrast values and Q_3 to the worst. We verify that Q_0 corresponds to the best Strehl average value, and that as our Q value increases (contrast gets worse), the value of Strehl decreases. This is consistent with what is described in the Sect. 3.1.4.

Fig. B.3. Most relevant environmental variables and their level of importance according to the calculation described in Sect. 3.1.4, where 1 is the maximum value if a particular variable had all the importance on the result. The greatest contribution is given by the Strehl, with an importance of 0.36.

Signal to Noise results with similar Strehl Ratio

Fig. B.4. Original SPHERE images showing our science target, HD 206893, and the targets delivering the three best and the worst results when used as reference in RSDI-PCA. The best is HD HD3003, with a Strehl of 0.84, delivering a S/N of 7.2, and the worst is HD 82943, with a Strehl of 0.82, and a S/N of 0.8. It is clearly visible that the image of this object has no similarity with our science target, despite having a similar Strehl ratio.

Appendix C: RSDI Using all SHARDDS as a reference cube

To identify what kind of results and outcomes we get using the whole SHARDDS as our reference cube is that we have calculated RSDI-PCA with 19119 frames and starting at 100 principal component numbers increasing by 200 each time, this is because it is a very large cube and its calculation time is long per iteration.

C.1. Figures

Fig. C.1. Reduced RSDI-PCA images using the all SHARRRDS data set as a reference cube with a total of 19119 frames with and different number of principal components (PCs). We can verify that the signal-to-noise ratio decreases as we increase the number of principal components, which is a product of the self-subtraction.

Fig. C.2. RSDI-PCA all SHARRRDS cube S/N plot showing a decreasing tendency as we increase the number of principal components, having a maximum value of 4.5 when we use 300 numbers of components, having a median value of -1.44.

Appendix D: Normalization Methods

To identify which type of normalization offered by VIP we should use, we made several tests using different reference libraries. First, we did a grid search to determine the optimal number of principal components to achieve the best S/N. We then calculated the contrast with different targets and normalization methods, verifying that temp-mean is the one that gives the best result.

The following figures show examples of S/N and contrast curves that justify the decision to use temp-mean.

D.1. Figures

Fig. D.1. Reduced RSDI-PCA images using different methods and different number of principal components (PCs). From the normalization methods we tested, none (left column), temp-mean (center) and spat-mean (right), we verify temp-mean delivers better S/N results. The libraries are identified by its image comparison and selection method in the following format: method_HD206893_N.R.

Fig. D.2. RSDI-PCA contrast curves of our science target HD 206893 using different libraries, normalization methods and number of principal components, as identified in the legend and title of the respective plot (HD 206893_N_R_method_pc). As also shown in Fig. D.1, the best performance is achieved with temp-mean.

Appendix E: Spectral Type Behavior

To identify the behavior and relevance of the spectral type, we studied the composition of the top 10 libraries from the PCC, which is presented as the best image selection method, obtaining the best signal-to-noise ratio results. We will also examine which spectral types are most prevalent and whether there are targets that frequently appear as reference cubes, along with their percentage in each case.

E.1. Figures

Fig. E.1. HD377 had the highest number of occurrences with 94 instances. This is followed by HD205674_2nd_epoch with 60 occurrences and HD145229 with 30 occurrences. HD60491 had 25 occurrences, while HD9672 was observed 11 times. HD221853 had 5 occurrences, HD201219 and HD37484 each had 3 occurrences. HD135599_3rd_epoch and HD84075 both had 1 occurrence each. G is the most dominant spectral type, representing approximately 54.9% of the total occurrences. F follows with about 29.2%, then K with 11.2%, and A with 4.7%. Thus, the spectral type G is the most dominant in the dataset, accounting for more than half of the total occurrences.

Analysis of the 10 Best Cubes

To understand the impact of checking the ten best cubes, we analyzed the distribution and characteristics of the reference stars used in these top-performing cubes. The following is a detailed explanation based on the data provided:

Provided Data

The 10 best cubes identified using the correlation technique are:

1. cube_libreria_corr_mask_HD206893_50_40
2. cube_libreria_corr_mask_HD206893_100_45
3. cube_libreria_corr_mask_HD206893_75_35
4. cube_libreria_corr_mask_HD206893_75_45
5. cube_libreria_corr_mask_HD206893_75_30
6. cube_libreria_corr_mask_HD206893_75_40
7. cube_libreria_corr_mask_HD206893_50_20
8. cube_libreria_corr_mask_HD206893_75_25
9. cube_libreria_corr_mask_HD206893_25_5
10. cube_libreria_corr_mask_HD206893_25_5

Fig. E.2. HD377 (G2V) had the highest total occurrences with 1,748 instances, followed by HD205674_2nd_epoch (F4IV) with 848 occurrences and HD145229 (G0) with 496 occurrences. Other notable stars include HD60491 (K2V) with 562 occurrences, HD9672 (A1V) with 386 occurrences, and HD221853 (F0) with 208 occurrences. HD201219 (G5) was recorded 78 times, HD37484 (F3V) 40 times, HD135599_3rd_epoch (K0V) 46 times, and HD84075 (G2V) 61 times. Less frequent occurrences were observed for AG_Tri_3rd_epoch (K8) with 18, HD25457 (F6V) with 7, HD122652 (F8) with 5, and both HD133803_2nd_epoch (A9V) and HD82943_2nd_epoch (F9V) with 2 occurrences each.

Fig. E.3. In terms of co-occurrences, HD377 (G2V), HD145229 (G0), HD60491 (K2V), HD9672 (A1V), HD221853 (F0), HD201219 (G5), HD37484 (F3V), and HD84075 (G2V) each appeared in 10 different files. HD25457 (F6V) appeared in 5 files, while HD122652 (F8) appeared in 3 different files.

Based on the totals, the spectral type G was the most dominant, with 2,383 occurrences, representing approximately 52.4% of the total occurrences. Spectral type F has 1,154 occurrences, accounting for about 25.4%. Spectral type K has 626 occurrences, accounting for approximately 13.8% of the total, while spectral type A has 388 occurrences, comprising around 8.5% of the total. The correlation metric method recognizes G-type stars as the best match. Despite being less represented in the dataset than F-type stars, G-type stars dominated the RDI process, highlighting their effectiveness as reference stars.